

Outstanding rices selected from 100 varieties tested for tolerance for high level of salt (17.5 mmho/cm at 25°C) at the seedling stage. RRS, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Treatment ^a	Root				Shoot			
		Length (cm)	Fresh wt (mg)	Dry wt (mg)	Water content (mg)	Length (cm)	Fresh wt (mg)	Dry wt (mg)	Water content (mg)
Patnai 23	N	16.6	215.0	19.0	196.0	14.4	172.5	27.0	145.5
	S	7.7	85.0	8.5	76.5	4.3	100.0	14.0	86.0
Dheral	N	23.6	103.7	28.3	75.5	25.7	211.3	64.3	147.0
	S	9.0	41.3	13.5	27.7	8.4	129.2	48.0	71.2
TN(I)	N	13.9	212.5	26.3	186.2	9.5	110.0	32.3	78.0
	S	2.2	6.5	3.0	33.4	0.6	12.5	4.3	7.2
IR8	N	15.5	231.7	27.5	203.2	12.5	166.6	40.5	125.1
	S	5.3	42.7	9.3	33.4	1.8	69.2	12.3	46.9
BPI76	N	14.4	135.0	18.5	116.5	7.8	102.5	23.5	79.0
	S	1.6	7.5	2.5	5.0	6.0	11.0	3.5	7.5
Marichsail	N	13.0	147.5	24.3	123.2	17.5	252.5	59.7	192.8
	S	6.7	41.5	12.0	29.5	6.5	121.7	41.0	80.7
Getu	N	15.6	172.5	21.5	151.0	11.9	135.0	23.5	111.5
	S	15.1	95.5	11.0	84.5	8.0	92.5	15.0	77.5
Damoder	N	16.4	93.0	22.0	71.0	16.5	167.5	31.0	136.5
	S	8.3	47.5	12.0	35.3	7.1	90.0	20.0	70.0
Dasal	N	17.8	165.0	30.0	135.0	15.6	160.0	29.0	131.0
	S	7.3	67.5	14.5	53.0	7.1	147.5	18.0	129.0
Dholabokra	N	21.6	217.5	26.5	191.0	22.4	252.5	48.5	204.0
	S	5.6	108.5	15.5	93.0	18.8	145.0	37.0	108.0
Hamilton	N	25.2	220.0	24.0	196.0	22.5	405.0	46.0	359.0
	S	15.9	197.5	13.0	184.5	13.7	215.0	37.5	177.5
SR 26 B	N	15.5	216.5	19.5	197.0	19.1	222.5	47.5	175.0
	S	6.5	100.0	10.0	90.0	6.6	135.0	20.0	115.0

^a N = normal water, S = saline water.

dry weight, closely followed by Hamilton and Dholabokra. Dholabokra had the maximum value for root dry weight.

Among the high yielding varieties, IR8 performed best. TN1 gave minimum values for most of the characteristics.

Hamilton was highly salt tolerant and BPI 76 was the least. Hamilton performed best on most of the characteristics. Because salinity appears to affect the rice plant most adversely at the seedling stage, this greenhouse technique can be profitably used to select salt-tolerant varieties. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Genetic control of submergence tolerance in rice

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The inheritance of submergence tolerance in rice was studied by analyzing the segregation pattern and estimating the genetic parameters of crosses involving the cultivars FR 13A, Kurkaruppan,

Thavalu, Gods Heenati, IR36, and B2433b-Kn-10-1-1-1.

Tests for submergence tolerance were conducted under artificial conditions by submerging 10-day-old seedlings for 7 days in 30-cm water. Water temperature was kept constant at 30°C, and light intensity was maintained at 400 lux at the tray level.

Segregation analyses indicated that at least three dominant genes were involved in the control of tolerance for submergence. Two had duplicate gene

action, and the third was complementary to either of the first two.

Estimation of the genetic parameters showed that additive and nonadditive gene effects were important in the inheritance of submergence tolerance. Dominance and nonallelic interactions were present in all crosses analyzed, and the nonallelic interactions were mostly of the duplicate type.

Estimates of broad sense heritability were low to moderate, indicating that a large portion of the phenotypic variance was due to nongenetic effects. ■

Response of traditional deepwater rice to nitrogen application

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Fertilization is a rare practice in most traditional, deepwater rice fields. Reports indicate positive nitrogen (N) response by some improved, deepwater rice lines in terms of grain yield. But such a response under variable water depths, especially in terms of uptake and utilization, is not well known.

IRRI greenhouse and field experiments indicate that high basal N in deepwater rice produces increased plant length and number of basal tillers. Those attributes are desirable in areas prone to early flooding where rapid elongation of the culm above water level is used to combat flood damage.

High basal tillers are retained in subsequent growth stages under both shallow (25-cm) and medium-deep (75-cm) water levels in a nonelongating type, such as IR42; and in deep (130-cm) water level in an elongating type such as Kalar Harsall. The high survival rate of basal tillers ultimately results in increased grain yields due to a higher number of panicles and spikelets per panicle (Table 1). High basal N also stimulates early nodal rooting and nodal tillering — which contributes to grain yields directly or indirectly by absorption of nutrients from floodwater — and additional panicles. This has been substantiated by production of additional nodal tillers and higher grain yields from topdressing with 40 ppm N